

EXPLICIT DYNAMIC RESPONSE OF DAMAGED BEAMS WITH APPLICATION TO UNCERTAIN AND IDENTIFICATION PROBLEMS

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Abstract

The influence of damage in beam like structures is a problem widely analysed in the literature in view of its importance towards the assessment of the residual carrying capacity and the evaluation of the inevitable changes of the dynamic properties. Usually, the dynamic properties and the forced vibrations of structures, cannot be explicitly inferred, particularly in presence of damage, since the computation of the roots of a highly nonlinear determinantal equation is preliminarily required. Rather, explicit formulations are usually preferred for their ease to use and the possibility to perform parametric analyses, very useful in the case of uncertain parameters, and also to address inverse problems. In this paper, aiming at proposing an explicit formulation of the dynamic response of cracked beams, a model which makes use of the distribution theory and does not require the enforcement of continuity conditions at the cracked sections, is employed. Approximated explicit expressions of the main modal parameters related to the crack severities are here provided and the reliability of the proposed formulas are verified with the exact solutions. The approximated modal parameters can then be used to obtain explicitly the forced vibrations of cracked beams. The proposed methodology is here adopted to address both direct and inverse problems. First, the variability of the dynamic response of cracked beams due to the presence of cracks with uncertain, but bounded, depths is investigated; then, upper and lower bounds of the response are evaluated by making use of both time and frequency domain analyses. In addition, the possibility to adopt the same explicit approach for the identification of damage intensities considering frequency measurements is explored.

Keywords: *Closed form solution, Response surface, Damage identification, Dynamic response, Generalised functions, Concentrated damage.*

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1 Introduction

One of the most dangerous aspects for the safety of structures is the presence of damage. The presence of impairments in a structure is often hidden and its magnitude can be mostly considered uncertain. For such a reason investigating how the structural response can be affected by a damage intensity represents a challenging issue whose solution can have a significant practical impact. To this aim, convenient and speedy re-analysis of damaged structures able to provide explicit information on the influence of damage parameters on the structural response is of crucial importance.

Damage can occur in structures under different forms, however, with regard to its spatial distribution it is commonly distinguished in accordance to a diffused or a concentrated pattern. Especially in presence of an early detection, or else when the damaged area is very limited, damage can be considered concentrated and it is usually referred to as a crack. In the latter case, one of the most widely adopted models to simulate the presence of cracks in a structure is the so called equivalent rotational hinge macroscopic model [1]-[10]. According to the equivalent hinge model a single crack, in straight as well as curved beams, can be modelled by disconnecting the two sides of the beam and inserting a rotational spring whose stiffness can be related to the crack depth according to different models [8]-[11]. The latter set up can be analysed by following the classical applications of beam-like structural models based on the Euler-Bernoulli or Timoshenko theories coupled with the enforcement of continuity conditions at the cracked sections. In this context, direct and inverse problems, and the relative computation of the exact frequencies, have been studied for beam-like structures as well as more complex structures such as frames [12],[13] by computing the roots of

a highly nonlinear determinantal equation or else by employing the Dynamic Stiffness Matrix (DSM) approach and the Wittrick & Williams algorithm [14],[15]. Nevertheless, according to the latter approaches, the problem size and the computational burden increase with the number of cracked cross sections. To overcome such an inconvenience, an effective way to treat discontinuities, due to concentrated cracks, is to adopt a mathematical distributional model which avoids enforcing continuity conditions at the cracked sections. Accordingly, boundary conditions are required at the two ends of the beam only, irrespectively of the along-axis cracks present in the beam. The distributional approach has been successfully applied by considering models based on a concentrated stiffness reduction [16] or a flexibility increase [17], proved to be equivalent to each other. Within the framework of generalised functions, similar strategies have been proposed in [18]-[21]; an alternative way to avoid the enforcement of continuity conditions at the discontinuous sections is the transfer matrix method as proposed in [22]. The advantage of the generalised function approach over the transfer matrix method consists in delivering explicit analytical formulations of response parameters of cracked beams and frames in terms of intensity, position and total number of the actual cracks. However, the latter explicit expressions, when dynamic analysis has to be dealt with, imply the knowledge of the system natural frequencies that, in turn, require the solution of a non linear determinantal equation which makes the dynamic analysis not fully explicit. For the latter reason, the generalised function approach has not been efficaciously employed so far to conduct parametric analysis, re-analysis, sensitivity assessment, interval analysis under uncertain parameters, or else inverse identification problems in an explicit manner for the case of cracked beams.

The motivation of this paper is deeply rooted in the need to get rid of the repetitive and cumbersome solution procedure of highly non linear eigenvalue problems, required by the generalised function approach for multiple cracked beams, when dynamic parametric analyses are to be conducted. The latter goal is pursued by proposing explicit expressions of the main modal parameters of multiple

cracked beams such as natural frequencies, generalised modal masses as well as modal load terms in case of forced vibrations. The proposed explicit expressions are formulated in terms of crack depth and they are based on the use of the Sherman and Morrison formula proposed in [23] for the inversion of matrices applied for the interpolation of the above mentioned response parameters over the range of crack depths to be investigated.

The proposed procedure exploits the capability of the generalised function approach to treat multiple cracked beams without addition of continuity conditions or degrees of freedom and, at the same time, provides an advancement towards explicit treatment of dynamic problems of such structures. The paper can be conceptually divided into four parts.

The first part presents the details of the procedure to obtain the explicit dependence of the natural frequencies, the generalised mass and the load term upon multiple crack depths.

The second part aims at showing the accuracy of the presented explicit expressions by comparing the proposed results with the exact values in terms of natural frequencies, generalised modal mass and modal load terms corresponding to different load distributions along the cracked beam axis. For the case of forced vibrations, due to the presence of an harmonic load, the accuracy of an entire response time history is also studied. In addition to the accuracy assessment, since the main peculiarity of the proposed explicit expressions lies in their advantage offered in case of analyses of beams with variable crack depths, the second part of the paper includes a detailed discussion of the reduced computational cost implied by the presented approach for different applications.

Based on the content of the first two parts, considering that stochastic structural mechanical properties may strongly affect the expected response [24],[25], hence a reasonable safety factor in the structural design and assessment should be guaranteed in this case, in the third part of the paper the problem of beams in presence of multiple cracks with uncertain depths is treated. A reliable exact tool for the dynamic analysis of structures with variable parameters is the spectral beam element; such a method is able to analyze wave propagation and to compute modal parameters and

was already applied to damaged beams [26]. In the field of uncertain parameters, alternatively to the probabilistic approach [27]-[29] and to the fuzzy logic [30], the method here employed, which also gained importance in the last years, is the interval analysis. It is based on the assumption that an uncertain parameter can vary within a given range, without assuming any probability content, and aims at identifying the corresponding bounds of a response parameter [31]-[33]. The interval analysis was applied to several problems related to the statics [34],[35] and the dynamic frequency response [36]-[38] of structures as well as transient analysis [39],[40] and, with regard to damaged structures, for inverse problems [41]. The direct problem for damaged beams, at least in the dynamic field, was treated in [42],[43] within the framework of a classic FEM approach. Specifically, in the third part of the paper the proposed approach is applied for the interval analysis of beams with multiple cracks whose depth is considered uncertain in a prescribed interval, performing both time and frequency domain analyses. In spite of the limited computational effort needed, it is shown how the proposed explicit approach is able to reproduce the bounds of the response otherwise to be computed according to an exact re-analysis, which is associated to a significantly higher computational burden. Remarkably, the proposed procedure is able to account for a non-monotonic relationship between input and output variables, so to cover the case in which the bounds of the response occur in correspondence of an internal point of the input variable interval, where convex analysis [39] or other simplified procedures fail.

Finally, due to its simplicity, since the proposed solution strategy lends itself to solve not only direct but also inverse problems, as a further availment of the proposed explicit solution, the conclusive fourth part of the manuscript is devoted to address the inverse problem aiming at the estimation of the crack depths once positions of damaged cross sections are known.

2 The governing equations of the forced vibrations of multi-cracked beams: closed form solution.

When a multi-cracked beam is considered, classic approaches require FEM analyses to obtain its response or, in the case continuum beam theory is resorted to, the enforcement of continuity conditions at the cracked sections. To make this procedure more effective, a model based on generalised functions is here employed as solution background taking advantage of a relevant solution strategy of the governing equations of a multi-cracked beam,. The adoption of a model of concentrated cracks is justified by the fact that the early detection of cracks in beams usually implies that cracks are still “small” and their extent is so limited that a concentrated crack model can be considered appropriate for the numerical modelling. Within this framework the equivalent hinge model is widely employed to this purpose, that is the beam is divided in chunks at the cracked sections and then connected by means of a rotational hinge [8]-[11]; the connected ends will undergo a jump rotation that can be related to the acting bending moment. The use of generalised functions, already adopted by some of the authors [16],[44], is here applied to the case of forced vibrations [45]. The solution, cast in explicit closed form and briefly recalled in the following, is unique and is provided in terms of four (boundary conditions dependent) integration constants only. Unlike classic approaches, it does not require any additional node or continuity condition at the cracked sections.

Let us consider an Euler-Bernoulli beam, with a spatial abscissa x spanning from 0 to the length L and distributed mass m , in presence of multiple cracks at $x_i, i = 1, \dots, n$, under a generic transverse load $\bar{q}(x, t)$.

The governing equation of the vibratory motion of the deterministic beam in terms of deflection function $v(x, t)$, with t time variable, is written as follows:

$$v^{IV}(x, t) + \frac{m}{E_o I_o} \ddot{v}(x, t) = \sum_{i=1}^n \Delta v'(x_i, t) \delta''(x - x_i) + \frac{\bar{q}(x, t)}{E_o I_o} \quad (1)$$

where a convenient model to account for the presence of rotational internal springs is employed by introducing unknown rotational discontinuities at the cracked sections on the right hand side of the equation as proposed in [19]. $\delta(\bullet)$ is the well known Dirac's delta distribution, the superimposed dot and the apex indicate temporal and spatial differentiations, respectively.

By introducing the normalised abscissa $\xi = x/L$ and the normalized deflection function $u(\xi, t) = v(x, t)/L$, the corresponding normalised governing equation is obtained:

$$u^{IV}(\xi, t) + \frac{mL^4}{E_o I_o} \ddot{u}(\xi, t) = \sum_{i=1}^n \Delta u'(\xi_i, t) \delta''(\xi - \xi_i) + q(\xi, t) \quad (2)$$

being $q(\xi, t) = \frac{\bar{q}(x, t)L^3}{E_o I_o}$ the normalized transversal load, see Figure 1. By introducing the

dimensionless crack compliance $\lambda_i = \frac{E_o I_o}{K_i L}$ (where K_i is the stiffness of the equivalent rotational

spring), the following relation, between the unknown rotations at the cracked sections and the relevant bending moments, holds:

$$\Delta u'(\xi_i, t) = \lambda_i u''(\xi_i, t) \quad (3)$$

The damage compliance parameters, which can be easily related to the damage severities as in [46], can then be collected in the vector $\lambda = [\lambda_1, \lambda_2, \dots, \lambda_i, \dots, \lambda_n]$.

Figure 1. Damaged beam subjected to a generic time-dependent external transverse load.

The generic r -th mode shape ϕ_r can be set forth by adopting the closed form expression inferred in [47] (neglecting the presence of any additional mass) where the dependency on the crack compliance vector λ is duly highlighted as follows:

$$\phi_r(\xi; \lambda) = \sum_{j=1}^4 C_{j,r}(\lambda) f_{j,r}(\xi; \lambda) \quad (4)$$

where $C_{j,r}(\lambda)$ represent the integration constants,

$$f_{j,r}(\xi; \lambda) = h_{j,r}(\xi; \lambda) + \sum_{i=1}^n \bar{h}_{i,r}(\xi; \lambda) \lambda_i f_{j,r}''(\xi_k; \lambda) \quad , \quad j=1, \dots, 4 \quad (5)$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} h_{1,r}(\xi; \lambda) &= \sin \alpha_r \xi; & h_{2,r}(\xi; \lambda) &= \cos \alpha_r \xi; & h_{3,r}(\xi; \lambda) &= \sinh \alpha_r \xi; & h_{4,r}(\xi; \lambda) &= \cosh \alpha_r \xi; \\ \bar{h}_{i,r}(\xi; \lambda) &= \frac{1}{2\alpha_r} [\sin \alpha_r (\xi - \xi_i) + \sinh \alpha_r (\xi - \xi_i)] U(\xi - \xi_i) \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

being $\alpha_r^4 = \omega_r^2 \frac{mL^4}{EI}$ the r -th frequency parameter depending on the boundary conditions of the beam and on its damage configuration, henceforth indicated as $\alpha_r^4(\lambda)$. Similar expressions of the mode shapes can be found in [20]. The functions $h_{j,r}(\xi; \lambda)$, $j=1, \dots, 4$, represent the solution of the homogeneous beam, while $\bar{h}_{i,r}(\xi; \lambda)$, $i=1, \dots, n$, represent additional functions able to account for the presence of the cracks.

It is worth to note that the mode shape ϕ_r , the integration constants $C_{j,r}$ and the functions $f_{j,r}$ rigorously depend not only on the crack severities collected in the vector λ , but also on their position ξ_k , $k=1, \dots, n$. The dependency on the crack locations is not explicitly listed to stress that they are assumed fixed parameters, on the contrary crack severities are considered variable parameters.

Once the eigenvalue problem of the multi-cracked beam is solved for the natural frequencies and modes [47], the response of the beam can be obtained through modal superposition and the displacement function is given by the following linear combination of the vibration modes:

$$u(\xi, t; \lambda) = \sum_{r=1}^{\infty} \phi_r(\xi; \lambda) z_r(t) \cong \sum_{r=1}^{n_m} \phi_r(\xi; \lambda) z_r(t) \quad (7)$$

being $z_r(t), r=1, \dots, \infty$ the modal coordinates. In the last term of Eq. (7) the approximated expression of the transversal displacement is provided by truncating the summation to a limited number n_m of modes as usually provided in the literature according to various criteria [48]. Replacing the modal superposition reported in Eq. (7) into Eq. (2) leads to the following expression:

$$\frac{mL^4}{E_o I_o} \sum_{r=1}^{n_m} \ddot{z}_r(t) \phi_r(\xi; \lambda) + \sum_{r=1}^{n_m} z_r(t) \left[\phi_r^{IV}(\xi; \lambda) - \sum_{i=1}^n \lambda_i \phi_r''(\xi_i; \lambda) \delta''(\xi - \xi_i) \right] = q(\xi, t) \quad (8)$$

By multiplying each term by a generic mode $\phi_p(\xi; \lambda)$ and integrating over the span in terms of normalized abscissa ξ , the following relationship can be obtained:

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{mL^4}{E_o I_o} \sum_{r=1}^{\infty} \ddot{z}_r(t) \int_0^1 \phi_r(\xi; \lambda) \phi_p(\xi; \lambda) d\xi + \\ & + \sum_{r=1}^{\infty} z_r(t) \int_0^1 \left[\phi_r^{IV}(\xi; \lambda) - \sum_{i=1}^n \lambda_i \phi_r''(\xi_i; \lambda) \delta''(\xi - \xi_i) \right] \phi_p(\xi; \lambda) d\xi = \int_0^1 \phi_p(\xi; \lambda) q(\xi, t) d\xi \end{aligned} \quad (9)$$

By exploiting the orthogonality properties of the modes (see Appendix A for the details), Eq. (9) becomes

$$\ddot{z}_p(t) + \omega_p^2(\lambda) z_p(t) = \frac{E_o I_o}{mL^4} \frac{Q_p(t; \lambda)}{M_p(\lambda)}, \quad p = 1, \dots, n_m \quad (10)$$

where $\omega_p(\lambda) = \sqrt{\frac{E_o I_o}{mL^4} \alpha_p^2(\lambda)}$ is the p -th natural frequency of the beam. In addition, the following two additional modal parameters, that is the generalized modal mass $M_p(\lambda)$ and the modal load term $Q_p(t; \lambda)$ are introduced as follows:

$$M_p(\lambda) = \int_0^1 \phi_p(\xi; \lambda) \phi_p(\xi; \lambda) d\xi \quad (11)$$

$$Q_p(t; \lambda) = \int_0^1 \phi_p(\xi; \lambda) q(\xi, t) d\xi \quad (12)$$

Without loss of generality, in the following two possible load configurations will be considered: a uniform load $q(\xi, t) = q_o(t)$ and a concentrated load $P_o(t) \delta(\xi - \xi_L)$ at the abscissa ξ_L . In these two cases Eq. (12) assumes the following forms, respectively:

$$\begin{aligned} q(\xi, t) = q_o(t) &\Rightarrow Q_p(t; \lambda) = q_o(t) \int_0^1 \phi_p(\xi; \lambda) d\xi \\ q(\xi, t) = P_o(t) \delta(\xi - \xi_L) &\Rightarrow Q_p(t; \lambda) = P_o(t) \phi_p(\xi_L; \lambda) \end{aligned} \quad (13)$$

Assuming a classical viscously damped model, the dissipation can be expressed by introducing modal damping ratios and Eq. (10) becomes:

$$\ddot{z}_p(t) + 2\zeta_p \omega_p(\lambda) \dot{z}_p(t) + \omega_p^2(\lambda) z_p(t) = \frac{E_o I_o}{mL^4} \frac{Q_p(t; \lambda)}{M_p(\lambda)} \quad (14)$$

being ζ_p the modal damping ratio associated to the generic p -th mode. The generic p -th modal coordinate, solution of Eq. (14), can be expressed as the summation of two contributions, that is a general solution $z_p^g(t)$ related to the free vibrations and depending on the initial conditions, given by

$$z_p^g(t) = e^{-\zeta_p \omega_p(\lambda) t} \left[z_p(0) \cos \omega_{p,d}(\lambda) t + \frac{\dot{z}_p(0) + \zeta_p \omega_p(\lambda) z_p(0)}{\omega_{p,d}(\lambda)} \sin \omega_{p,d}(\lambda) t \right] \quad (15)$$

which decays in time due to the negative exponential term, and a particular solution $z_p^p(t)$ depending on the load term. In Eq. (15) the damped frequency $\omega_{p,d}(\lambda) = \omega_p(\lambda) \sqrt{1 - \zeta_p^2}$ is introduced. In the case of real structures, even in presence of small damping, the free vibration term motion rapidly tends to disappear and the response due to the load term prevails. The particular solution $z_p^p(t)$ of Eq. (14) depends on the form of the load term on the right-hand side. When a constant load is considered, either concentrated or distributed, the load term is constant; when a

harmonic law is considered (with a dimensional pulsation ω and a corresponding dimensionless counterpart $\alpha_\omega^4 = \omega^2 \frac{mL^4}{EI}$), both for a concentrated or distributed load, the particular integral attains a harmonic form representing the steady state response. A summary of the possible load terms associated to these relevant load distributions is reported in the first two columns of Table 1. The third column reports the steady state response according to the related modal load term. In all the reported formulas the frequency ratio parameter $\eta_p(\lambda) = \alpha_\omega^2 / \alpha_p^2(\lambda) = \omega / \omega_p(\lambda)$ has been introduced.

Table 1. Load distribution, relevant load terms and particular integrals

$q(\xi, t)$	$\frac{Q_p(t; \lambda)}{M_p(\lambda)}$	$z_p^p(t)$
$P_o \delta(\xi - \xi_o)$	$\frac{P_o \phi_p(\xi_o; \lambda)}{M_p(\lambda)}$	$z_p^p(t) = \frac{P_o \phi_p(\xi_o; \lambda)}{M_p(\lambda) \alpha_p^4(\lambda)}$
q_o	$\frac{q_o \int_0^1 \phi_p(\xi; \lambda) d\xi}{M_p(\lambda)}$	$z_p^p(t) = \frac{q_o \int_0^1 \phi_p(\xi; \lambda) d\xi}{M_p(\lambda) \alpha_p^4(\lambda)}$
$P_o \delta(\xi - \xi_o) \sin \omega t$	$\frac{P_o \phi_p(\xi_o; \lambda)}{M_p(\lambda)} \sin \omega t$	$z_p^p(t) = \frac{P_o \phi_p(\xi_o; \lambda)}{M_p(\lambda) \alpha_p^4(\lambda)} [C_p(\lambda) \sin \omega t + D_p(\lambda) \cos \omega t]$
$q_o \sin \omega t$	$\frac{q_o \int_0^1 \phi_p(\xi; \lambda) d\xi}{M_p(\lambda)} \sin \omega t$	$z_p^p(t) = \frac{q_o \int_0^1 \phi_p(\xi; \lambda) d\xi}{M_p(\lambda) \alpha_p^4(\lambda)} [C_p(\lambda) \sin \omega t + D_p(\lambda) \cos \omega t]$

In particular, rows 1 and 3 refer to the case of a concentrated load assuming a constant and a pulsating intensity, respectively; rows 2 and 4 refer to the case of a distributed load assuming a constant and a pulsating intensity, respectively. In all the four considered cases, the modal coordinates in the third column are expressed for the more general case of damped systems. The

two terms $C_p(\lambda)$ and $D_p(\lambda)$ appearing in Table 1 and characterizing the steady-state responses of pulsating loads are given by:

$$\begin{aligned} C_p(\lambda) &= \frac{1 - \eta_p^2(\lambda)}{[1 - \eta_p^2(\lambda)]^2 + [2\zeta_p \eta_p(\lambda)]^2} \\ D_p(\lambda) &= \frac{-2\zeta_p \eta_p(\lambda)}{[1 - \eta_p^2(\lambda)]^2 + [2\zeta_p \eta_p(\lambda)]^2} \end{aligned} \quad (16)$$

The integration constants appearing in Eq. (4) can be obtained by enforcing the relevant boundary conditions. Without loss of generality, here two cases corresponding to a statically indeterminate beam and to a statically determinate one are elucidated. For the case of a clamped-clamped beam, the boundary conditions are as follows:

$$\phi(0; \lambda) = 0; \quad \phi'(0; \lambda) = 0; \quad \phi(1; \lambda) = 0; \quad \phi'(1; \lambda) = 0 \quad (17)$$

After some algebra, the characteristic equation can be written in the following form

$$\begin{aligned} [f_{3,r}(1; \lambda) - f_{1,r}(1; \lambda)][f'_{4,r}(1; \lambda) - f'_{2,r}(1; \lambda)] + \\ - [f_{4,r}(1; \lambda) - f_{2,r}(1; \lambda)][f'_{3,r}(1; \lambda) - f'_{1,r}(1; \lambda)] = 0 \end{aligned} \quad (18)$$

which, once a certain configuration of damage severities λ is given, can be numerically solved in terms of frequency parameters $\alpha_r(\lambda)$ and the integration constants inferred by solving the algebraic system in Eq. (17).

For the simpler case of a pinned-pinned beam the boundary conditions are as follows:

$$\phi(0; \lambda) = 0; \quad \phi''(0; \lambda) = 0; \quad \phi(1; \lambda) = 0; \quad \phi''(1; \lambda) = 0 \quad (19)$$

which lead to the following characteristic equation

$$f_{1,r}(1; \lambda) f''_{3,r}(1; \lambda) - f_{3,r}(1; \lambda) f''_{1,r}(1; \lambda) = 0 \quad (20)$$

Once the frequency parameters are numerically computed by Eq. (20), the corresponding four integration constants can be inferred accordingly by solving the system in Eq. (19).

3 An explicit approximated approach for the evaluation of the modal parameters

The treatment of beams based on the use of generalised function, presented in the previous section, provides a convenient tool to deal with the presence of multiple cracks and perform relevant dynamic analyses. However, dynamic analyses to assess the variability of the response variability in terms of crack depths requires repetitive cumbersome evaluation of the modal parameters. For the latter reason, within the framework of the previous generalised function approach, an explicit formulation of the cracked beam modal properties is proposed in this section and its accuracy is duly verified also in terms of full time histories.

The availability of explicit solutions, although approximated, has an impact both in direct and inverse problems. In direct problems it can be very useful for sensitivity analyses and when re-analysis of the structure is required [49]. In the field of inverse problems there are numerous procedures which are able to identify the crack position [47] with reasonable precision, on the other hand their severity is much more difficult to identify and for this reason it is convenient to formulate a procedure able to deliver expressions of the modal properties as well as the dynamic response of damaged beams explicitly formulated in terms of crack intensities. Therefore, in this section and in the next one, a novel explicit solution procedure for the dynamic response of beams is pursued in order to provide information regarding the response variability as well as to serve for crack intensity identification purposes.

3.1. Proposed approximate explicit solution

In order to derive an approximate explicit dependence of the main modal parameters of a damaged beam upon the damage intensities, some additional parameters have to be defined. In particular, the generic variable λ_i is characterized by a reference value $\lambda_{o,i}$ and two other values, a lower and an upper value, identified as $\underline{\lambda}_i$ and $\overline{\lambda}_i$, respectively, which will be of help to enforce the coincidence

between approximated and exact solutions for some damage configurations. $\underline{\lambda}_i$ and $\bar{\lambda}_i$ are characterized by a symmetric deviation amplitude $\Delta\lambda_i$ with respect to the reference value, therefore the following relationships hold:

$$\begin{aligned}\lambda_{o,i} &= \frac{1}{2}(\underline{\lambda}_i + \bar{\lambda}_i) \\ \Delta\lambda_i &= \frac{1}{2}(\bar{\lambda}_i - \underline{\lambda}_i)\end{aligned}\quad (21)$$

The i -th crack severity λ_i can be considered as a function of a continuous variable β_i representing the fluctuation with respect to the reference value $\lambda_{o,i}$:

$$\lambda_i = \lambda_{o,i} + \beta_i \quad (22)$$

The variability of the modal parameters with respect to the cracks severities are needed to compute the response of the beam. In particular, for the generic p -th mode, the frequency parameter $\alpha_p^4(\boldsymbol{\lambda})$, the generalized modal mass $M_p(\boldsymbol{\lambda})$ (see Eq. (11)), and the load term $Q_p(t; \boldsymbol{\lambda})$ (see Eq. (12)), have to be evaluated. Since the exact determination of such parameters would require cumbersome analyses, i.e. finding the roots of the characteristic equation for the frequency parameters $\alpha_p^4(\boldsymbol{\lambda})$, and the integral of the p -th mode shape computation, in the following an approximated but explicit solution is proposed to evaluate the mentioned modal parameters.

Let us consider the case of a generic cracked beam with severities $\boldsymbol{\lambda} = [\lambda_1, \lambda_2, \dots, \lambda_i, \dots, \lambda_n]$ assumed as variable parameters according to the model introduced in the Eqs. (21) and (22).

The following interpolating Sherman and Morrison formula [23] for the inversion of matrices, already exploited for structural problems in [32],[50], is adapted for the problem at hand so to provide an estimation of the frequency parameters as functions of the damage configuration according to the following relationship:

$$\alpha_p^4(\boldsymbol{\lambda}) \cong \alpha_{o,p}^4 + \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{\beta_i a_{p,i}}{1 + \beta_i b_{p,i}} \quad , \quad p = 1, \dots, n_m \quad (23)$$

being $\alpha_{o,p}^4$ the p -th frequency parameter associated to the reference distribution $\lambda_o = [\lambda_{o,1}, \lambda_{o,2}, \dots, \lambda_{o,n}]$ of damage, whereas $a_{p,i}, b_{p,i}$ represent two appropriate sets of coefficients. These will be evaluated explicitly later in this section by enforcing the correspondence between exact values and approximate expression of the frequency parameters at $2n$ significant damage configurations following a response surface procedure. Each of the n pairs of these configurations is defined as follows by considering the reference value of all the damage intensities but the s -th one which is set to upper and lower values:

$$\begin{aligned}\bar{\lambda}_s &= [\lambda_{o,1}, \lambda_{o,2}, \dots, \bar{\lambda}_s, \dots, \lambda_{o,n}] \\ \underline{\lambda}_s &= [\lambda_{o,1}, \lambda_{o,2}, \dots, \underline{\lambda}_s, \dots, \lambda_{o,n}]\end{aligned}\quad s = 1, \dots, n \quad (24)$$

Once the approximated p -th frequency parameter is computed by means of Eq. (23), the relevant approximated mode shapes are explicitly provided by Eqs. (4)-(6). The generalized modal mass $M_p(\lambda)$ and the modal load term $Q_p(t; \lambda)$, given in Eqs. (11) and (12) can then be obtained by considering two possible strategies:

- i)* a numerical integration (for example by means of recursive adaptive Simpson quadrature);
- ii)* by means of an approximated strategy consistent with that adopted for the frequency parameters in Eq. (23).

The first approach guarantees a better match with the exact value, but it implies the loss of an explicit dependency on the crack intensities; on the other hand, the approximating strategy ensures an explicit dependency of the modal parameters on the crack intensities according to the following formulas:

$$M_p(\lambda) \cong M_{o,p} + \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{\beta_i c_{p,i}}{1 + \beta_i d_{p,i}}, \quad p = 1, \dots, n_m \quad (25)$$

$$Q_p(t; \lambda) \cong Q_{o,p}(t) + \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{\beta_i e_{p,i}(t)}{1 + \beta_i f_{p,i}(t)}, \quad p = 1, \dots, n_m \quad (26)$$

where the notation adopted for the frequency parameter approximations holds for these two other cases.

The set of coefficients $a_{p,i}, b_{p,i}, c_{p,i}, d_{p,i}$ and $e_{p,i}(t), f_{p,i}(t)$, are explicitly obtained by following the procedure outlined in what follows based on the solution of a set of linear equations. In particular, without loss of generality, the procedure is presented with reference to the adopted frequency parameter approximation, but it can be also applied to obtain the parameters for the generalized modal mass and for the load terms too.

In view of the interpolation formula proposed in Eq. (23), by enforcing the correspondence between exact and approximated expressions of the frequency parameters for the considered $2n$ damage configurations $\underline{\lambda}_s, \bar{\lambda}_s, s = 1, \dots, n$ reported in Eq. (24) the following two-variable linear system is obtained:

$$\begin{aligned}\alpha_p^4(\bar{\lambda}_s) &= \alpha_{o,p}^4 + \frac{\Delta\lambda_s a_{p,s}}{1 + \Delta\lambda_s b_{p,s}} \\ \alpha_p^4(\underline{\lambda}_s) &= \alpha_{o,p}^4 - \frac{\Delta\lambda_s a_{p,s}}{1 - \Delta\lambda_s b_{p,s}}\end{aligned}\quad (27)$$

where $p = 1, \dots, n_m$ and $\alpha_p^4(\bar{\lambda}_s), \alpha_p^4(\underline{\lambda}_s)$ represent the p -th frequency parameters associated to $\lambda = \underline{\lambda}_s$ and $\lambda = \bar{\lambda}_s$, respectively. n systems of two equations, as those in Eq. (27) lead, after some algebra, to the n pairs of coefficients $a_{p,s}, b_{p,s}$ which assume the following expressions:

$$\begin{aligned}a_{p,s} &= \frac{2}{\Delta\lambda_s} \frac{[\alpha_p^4(\bar{\lambda}_s) - \alpha_{o,p}^4][\alpha_{o,p}^4 - \alpha_p^4(\underline{\lambda}_s)]}{\alpha_p^4(\bar{\lambda}_s) - \alpha_p^4(\underline{\lambda}_s)} \\ b_{p,s} &= \frac{1}{\Delta\lambda_s} \frac{2\alpha_{o,p}^4 - \alpha_p^4(\underline{\lambda}_s) - \alpha_p^4(\bar{\lambda}_s)}{\alpha_p^4(\bar{\lambda}_s) - \alpha_p^4(\underline{\lambda}_s)}\end{aligned}\quad p = 1, \dots, n_m, \quad s = 1, \dots, n \quad (28)$$

Similarly, the following relationships are inferred:

$$c_{p,s} = \frac{2}{\Delta\lambda_s} \frac{[M_p(\bar{\lambda}_s) - M_{o,p}][M_{o,p} - M_p(\underline{\lambda}_s)]}{M_p(\bar{\lambda}_s) - M_p(\underline{\lambda}_s)} \quad (29)$$

$$d_{p,s} = \frac{1}{\Delta\lambda_s} \frac{2M_{o,p} - M_p(\underline{\lambda}_s) - M_p(\bar{\lambda}_s)}{M_p(\bar{\lambda}_s) - M_p(\underline{\lambda}_s)}$$

$$e_{p,s}(t) = \frac{2}{\Delta\lambda_s} \frac{[Q_p(t; \bar{\lambda}_s) - Q_{o,p}(t)][Q_{o,p}(t) - Q_p(t; \underline{\lambda}_s)]}{Q_p(t; \bar{\lambda}_s) - Q_p(t; \underline{\lambda}_s)} \quad (30)$$

$$f_{p,s}(t) = \frac{1}{\Delta\lambda_s} \frac{2Q_{o,p}(t) - Q_p(t; \underline{\lambda}_s) - Q_p(t; \bar{\lambda}_s)}{Q_p(t; \bar{\lambda}_s) - Q_p(t; \underline{\lambda}_s)}$$

3.2. Validation of the proposed approach: modal properties

In order to assess the accuracy of the proposed approximation, for the evaluation of the modal parameters, two simple cases are considered herein, concerning a clamped-clamped and a simply supported beam.

Table 2. Reference values of the main modal properties for the beam reported in Figure 2a.

p	$\alpha_{o,p}^4$	$M_{o,p}$	$Q_{o,p}$
1	498.34	1.074	1.143
2	3257.52	0.850	-1.311
3	12315.67	1.108	1.051
4	35523.70	1.769	0.349
5	86618.26	1.645	-1.769

Figure 2. Comparison between exact and approximated modal properties for a (a) statically indeterminate beam: (b) frequency parameter and (c) relative error, (d) generalized modal mass and (e) relative error, (f) load term and (g) relative error.

Figure 2 shows the results associated to the case of a clamped-clamped beam, with a crack located at $\xi_1 = 0.2$ associated to a reference severity $\lambda_{o,1} = 0.15$; the amplitude for the damage severity fluctuation is $\Delta\lambda_1 = 0.15$ (Figure 2a). A concentrated transversal unit step load is applied at the abscissa $\xi_o = 0.7$. In Figures 2b, 2d, 2f exemplify the comparison between exact (solid line) and approximated (dashed line) parameters by Eqs. (23),(25) and (26) for the first five frequencies: frequency parameters (Figure 2b), generalized modal mass (Figure 2d) and load term (Figure 2f). All the terms are normalized by the reference value reported in Table 2. In Figure 2c, 2e, 2g the corresponding relative errors are reported.

It is worth to note that the results are shown in the range $\lambda_1 \in [0, 0.3]$, which, corresponds according to the equivalent spring model proposed in [47] to a normalized notch depth $d/h \in [0, 0.48]$ if the slenderness of the beam h/L is set to 0.1.

Analogous results are reported in Figure 3 for a pinned-pinned cracked beam ($\xi_1 = 0.4$, $\lambda_{o,1} = 0.2$, $\Delta\lambda_1 = 0.2$) subjected to a distributed uniform unit step load $q_o = 1$. The uniform load is applied on half of the beam. The reference values of the modal properties are reported in Table 3.

Table 3. Reference values of the main modal properties for the beam reported in Figure 3a.

p	$\alpha_{o,p}^4$	$M_{o,p}$	$Q_{o,p}$
1	71.35	0.492	0.328
2	1411.81	0.677	0.348
3	7162.37	0.371	0.108
4	20390.14	0.717	-0.009
5	60880.68	0.500	0.064

Figure 3. Comparison between exact and approximated modal properties for a (a) statically determinate beam: (b) frequency parameter and (c) relative error, (d) generalized modal mass and (e) relative error, (f) load term and (g) relative error.

Finally, the case of a double cracked beam is considered in Figure 4 to show how the error associated to the approximated modal properties does not change significantly as the number of cracks

increases. Namely, another crack located at $\xi_2 = 0.7$ with a reference severity $\lambda_{o,2} = 0.1$ is added to the beam analyzed in Figure 3. The fluctuation of the additional crack has amplitude $\Delta\lambda_2 = 0.1$. In Figure 4 the asterisks indicate the damaged where the approximate solution is enforced to replicate the exact one (i.e. zero error).

Figure 4. Comparison between exact and approximated modal properties (first three frequencies) for a (a) double cracked statically determinate beam: (b) relative percentage errors in terms of frequency parameter (first column), generalized modal mass (second column) and load term (third column).

3.3. Validation of the proposed approach: time history

In order to provide a further validation the time history computed according to the proposed approach are compared with the exact one.

To this purpose, the single cracked beam reported in Figure 3a and subjected to a pulsating distributed load, with intensity $q_o \sin \omega t$ ($q_o = 1, \omega = 5 \text{ rad/s}$), acting on the left half of the beam is considered. As response parameter, the transversal displacement $u(\xi_r, t; \lambda)$ with $\xi_r = 0.5$ is adopted; in addition, the first five frequencies with an associated damping equal to 0.05 are accounted for. The results are computed according to the set of physical data corresponding to a beam with the following characteristics: $L=5 \text{ m}$, $E=2.1 \cdot 10^{11} \text{ N/m}^2$, $I= 8.33 \cdot 10^{-6} \text{ m}^4$, $m= 75 \text{ kg/m}$. The same data are employed in the applications reported in the next subsections 5.1 and 5.2.

In Figure 5a the exact time history (continuous line) and the approximated one (dashed line) are compared for an intensity of the damage $\lambda_1 = 0.05$. Such a damage intensity corresponds to a value of the damage associated to the highest difference with respect to the exact solution in terms of frequency parameter, generalized modal mass and load term (Figures 3c,e,g). Figure 5a shows that the two solutions are very close to each other. Figure 5b depicts the difference between the proposed solution and the exact one normalized by the maximum achieved displacement. As expected, the error tends to cumulate with time; however, even considering the entire time span (a total amount of 1000 time steps) the maximum error is lower than 0.5%, which is comparable with the error of the corresponding modal properties, Figures 3c,e,g.

Figure 5. Time histories for the beam reported in Figure 3a: (a) comparison between exact and approximated results, (b) relative error.

4 On the use of the explicit evaluation of the dynamic response: computational advantage

The proposed formulation provided an explicit form for the modal parameters of a multiple cracked beam. However, as shown in the previous section, a generic response parameter $r(\xi_r, t; \lambda)$ at a desired abscissa ξ_r of a damaged beam subjected to forced vibrations can also be obtained explicitly, as shown in the previous application in terms of transversal displacements. In this section,

by analysing the details of the procedure to evaluate a response parameter time history, the computational advantage of the proposed procedure with respect to other formulations is discussed. In order to obtain a response parameter $r(\xi_r, t; \lambda)$ the relevant modal parameters have to be computed and then the response via model superposition can be computed as follows:

$$r(\xi_r, t; \lambda) = \sum_{p=1}^{n_m} \phi_p^k(\xi_r; \lambda) z_p(t) \quad (31)$$

being k the order of the derivative associated to desired response $r(\xi_r, t; \lambda)$. Depending on the value assumed by k , the response in terms of deflection ($k = 0$), rotation ($k = 1$), bending moment ($k = 2$), shear force ($k = 3$) can be inferred. In particular, by replacing $k = 0$ in Eq. (31), Eq. (7) can be obtained as particular case.

Eq. (31), if no explicit approach is at hand, requires the computation of the modal parameters introduced in section 2, according to the considered damage configuration; such parameters can be rigorously inferred through the *nonlinear determination of modal properties*, which requires highly nonlinear calculations, that is:

i) to determine the frequency parameters $\alpha_p^2(\lambda)$, through the solution of a highly nonlinear determinantal equation (see Eqs. (18) and (20)) considering the computation of an adequate number of roots corresponding to the desired number of modal properties to be obtained; the eigenmodes $\phi_p(\xi; \lambda)$ can then be straightforwardly evaluated according to Eqs. (4-6);

ii) to determine the generalized modal mass $M_p(\lambda)$, by means of the solution of a definite integral (see Eq. (11)) which can be rigorously solved but requires tricky computations;

iii) to determine the load term $Q_p(t; \lambda)$, with the solution of a definite integral (see Eq. (12)) which, in the case of time histories, has to be solved at each time step unless the variables t and ξ are uncoupled.

If a single deterministic analysis with given parameters has to be performed, the standard procedure is the best manner to get reliable results, since the nonlinear determination of modal properties has to be run just for the specific damage configuration under consideration. Thus, the proposed approximated strategy, built on three runs of the standard procedure, would turn out to be disadvantageous.

On the other hand, for direct problems requiring sensitivity or parametric analyses (and for inverse problems, as better shown in section 6), the proposed procedure has considerable advantages with respect to a standard rigorous approach which requires a cumbersome re-analysis.

In fact, it is worth to mention that, in absence of explicit formulations, an exact re-analysis strategy able to provide a complete response surface of the damaged beam requires the nonlinear determination of modal properties for a very large number of damage configurations. Hence, the simplest possible criterion to reconstruct the response surface is choosing evenly spaced values of the variable parameters, and thus performing a Monte Carlo simulation as better detailed in section 5. In this context, considering for instance a constant number of possible damage intensities for each crack n_d , the amount of nonlinear determinations of modal properties is n_d^n . It is worth to mention that in the case of re-analysis an exponential dependency on the number of cracks is observed;

On the other hand, the proposed strategy based on the formulation of explicit expression of the modal parameters, requires the performance of nonlinear determinations of modal properties only for $2n+1$ damage configurations hence showing a linear dependence on the number of cracks (see Table 4 for a comparison).

A significant problem to which the proposed approach can be advantageously applied (see section 5) is the search for the bounds of the response when one or more parameters of the structure are considered uncertain but bounded. One of the most widely employed strategies to accomplish this purpose is the well-known vertex method, which is a robust approach when the response is a monotonic function of the uncertain parameters. In this case all possible combinations of the lower

and upper bounds of the uncertain parameters have to be explored; for the treated case, that is the dynamic response of a damaged beam with uncertain crack intensities, the vertex method would imply evaluating the modal properties of the beam for 2^n damage configurations. An interesting alternative approach, based on the evidence that the eigenvalues are monotonic functions of the uncertain damage intensities, is proposed in [43] making use of FE models; the authors employ just two analyses (associated to the damage distributions characterized by the lowest and to the highest damage intensities, respectively) to approximately assess the bounds of the response of the forced vibrations of damaged beams. A summary of the computational burden associated to all the possible mentioned methods here considered is reported in Table 4.

Table 4. Computational burden associated to the re-analysis and the proposed strategy in terms of nonlinear determination of modal properties.

	Nonlinear determination of modal properties
Re-analysis	n_d^n
Proposed strategy	$2n+1$
Vertex method	2^n
Approach proposed in [43]	2

Nevertheless, in the forced vibrations of beams the response cannot be always assumed as a monotonic function of any input data which affect the modal properties of the beam. This is mainly due to resonance effects which can lead to very large amplitude of the response parameters for any intermediate value of the considered uncertain parameters. Then, the only general approach to assess the dynamic response of excited beams among those reported in Table 4 are the exact re-analysis and the explicit approach here proposed. They will be compared in the numerical applications.

Precisely, the computation of the bounds of the response performed by means an exact approach implies computing, for each time step, the response parameter for given damage configurations (computation of the response according to Eqs. (7),(15) in the case of time histories and according to the formulas of Table 1 in the case of response spectra) and then considering, among the finite

number of responses, the maximum and minimum values (this is the only possible strategy in the case of exact re-analysis).

On the other hand, when an explicit expression of the response surface is at hand and a continuous function is obtained, a more accurate evaluation of bounds of the response can be obtained solving a maximum/minimum constrained problem for each time step (for the case of time histories) or for each pulsation (for the case of the response spectra). The solution of this constrained problem is here solved by means of the algorithm described in [51]. It is worth to note that this strategy is not mandatory but is here adopted for its ease to be pursued and since its adoption does not imply a significant increase of the computational burden; even for the case of response spectra, and in particular when the resonance effects occur, the constrained nonlinear multivariable minimum problem is very effective and does not imply any slowdown as well as any loss of convergence.

Within the re-analysis strategy, a further remark to be arisen is that there are many possible criteria to select the considered damage configurations aiming at a precise identification of the bounds of the response; here evenly spaced steps of the uncertain parameters are considered. No specific algorithm is adopted to identify the values to which the bounds of the response are associated; however, any algorithm aiming at a more accurate search for the bounds of the response would require to be executed at each time step of the time histories (or for each considered pulsation in the case of the response spectra), thus further increasing the computational burden associated to the standard procedure, see Table 4.

More concisely, the proposed explicit strategy allows applying analytical methods for the search of the bounds, thus avoiding any cumbersome numerical re-analysis procedure and numerical search of the bounds of the response.

5 Application to direct problems

The explicit approach described in the previous sections is here applied with reference to different meaningful applications for the forced vibration analysis of damaged beams. The presented applications are concerning with the search for the bounds of response parameters within given intervals of the crack depths both in terms of time histories and response spectra.

In subsection 5.1 the bounds of the response of a damaged beam will be assessed and compared with the response computed by scanning the damage intensity interval and applying the exact deterministic analysis for each value. In this case both the transient and the steady-state responses will be accounted for. Then, in subsection 5.2, with reference to the steady-state response only, spectra of the response for damaged beams subjected to pulsating loads will be proposed and compared again with the results obtained through the deterministic response associated to the scanning of the damage configurations at given steps.

It will be shown how the bounds of the response are not always associated to the bounds of the intervals of the crack depth parameter, thus proving that the procedure is more robust than other approaches.

5.1. Interval time-domain response

The applications proposed in section 3 show that the formulas reported in Eqs. (23),(25),(26) provide accurate approximations of the main modal parameters characterizing a beam subjected to an external load. However, the final goal of this subsection is the exploitation of those explicit expressions for proper interval time history analyses considering uncertainties in the damage severities at the cracked sections. Therefore, the effectiveness of the proposed approximated solution is assessed by comparing the bounds of the response computed according to a scanning exact procedure with those obtained through the procedure proposed in section 4.

The beam considered in the section 3 is here further investigated. Precisely, the interval time-domain response in terms of transversal displacement of the middle span cross section of for the beam depicted in Figure 3a has been conducted and the results reported in Figure 6. In the latter figure a comparison between the results associated to an exact re-analysis and the response bounds obtained with the proposed approach is reported. In Figure 6a,b the grey area represents the ensemble of the exact responses computed by scanning the damage intensities at evenly spaced steps $\Delta\tilde{\lambda}_1 = 0.01$. The contour of the grey area represents the envelope of the time response preferably to be captured by less cumbersome procedures. For convenience, the exact responses for the reference value, and those associated to the lowest and the highest crack severities (i.e. $\lambda_1 = 0$, $\lambda_1 = 0.4$) are reported in Figure 6a with continuous, dashed, and dashdot lines, respectively. In fact, the last two analyses are those corresponding to the adoption of the vertex method. It may be noticed that the bounds of the responses identified by the contour of the grey area cannot be identified by simply running the three mentioned exact analyses, and even running a larger number of analyses for given values of damage severities (in this case 41 exact analyses were run), the correct bounds of the response can be identified only in an approximate way. Theoretically the correct bounds of the response would require a very large number of analyses. Conversely, in Figure 6b the bounds of the response are computed according to the proposed procedure outlined in section 3. Such a procedure requires to compute the exact modal properties for three values of damage severities (namely $\lambda_1 = 0, \lambda_1 = 0.2, \lambda_1 = 0.4$) and then to solve two maximum/minimum conditioned problems for each time step, thus strongly limiting the required computational burden. The relevant lower and upper bounds are reported with the blue dashed and dashdot lines, respectively. It is worth to mention that in this case the exact time histories associated to the crack depth bounds and the lower and upper bounds obtained by means of the proposed approach provide a similar accuracy when compared to the grey area. However, the advantage of the proposed approach will be more evident in the subsequent applications.

Figure 6. Interval time-domain response (grey area obtained with a full re-analysis) for the beam reported in Figure 3a. Comparison with (a) exact analyses associated to boundary intensities of damage and (b) response bounds obtained with the proposed approach.

To demonstrate the usefulness of the proposed explicit solution the dependency of the normalized transversal deflection of the middle span cross section on the crack intensity is reported in Figure 7 for two instants of the interval time-domain response reported in Figure 6. In particular, in Figure 7a the time step $t=0.3$ s is considered, where a monotonic trend of the monitored displacement with respect to the damage intensity is encountered. In this case exact re-analysis (continuous line) and approximated solution (dashed line) lead to very close results. On the other hand, in Figure 7b the

results associated to $t=5.9$ s are reported; in this case the dependency of the response parameter on the damage intensity is not monotonic, and several relative maxima/minima are encountered. The latter aspect might hinder an expeditious search of the absolute bounds of the response with a trial and error strategy, even supported by a searching algorithm. Exact and approximated solutions provide very similar results for the damage intensity values employed in the re-analysis; nonetheless, the undoubted advantage of having at hand a continuous explicit function of the response parameter is here demonstrated since the proposed strategy allows a quick and effective search of the bounds of the response through one of the search algorithms available in the literature [51].

Figure 7. Crack intensity vs normalized deflection for the beam reported in Figure 3a for specific time steps: (a) $t=0.3$ s and (b) $t=5.9$ s.

When more than one crack is considered the advantages offered by the proposed procedure are even more evident. To this purpose, in Figure 8 the results relative to a pinned-pinned double cracked beam as reported in Figure 8a and subjected to a concentrated pulsating load acting on the midpoint of the beam, $q(\xi, t) = P_o \delta(\xi - \xi_L) \sin \omega t$ ($P_o = 1$, $\xi_L = 0.5$, $\omega = 10 \text{ rad/s}$), are reported. The two cracks are located at $\xi_1 = 0.2$ and $\xi_2 = 0.7$, respectively, and are both characterized by the reference intensity $\lambda_1 = \lambda_2 = 0.05$. The approximated modal parameters are computed considering a fluctuation amplitude $\Delta\lambda_1 = \Delta\lambda_2 = 0.05$. Again, the grey area represents the envelope of the exact responses computed scanning the damage intensities at evenly spaced steps $\Delta\tilde{\lambda}_1 = \Delta\tilde{\lambda}_2 = 0.01$; therefore, 121 exact analyses were performed, that is the computational burden increases with the second power of the number of cracks. On the other hand, the results relative to the interval analysis obtained with the proposed approach require the computation of the exact modal parameters for five configurations, that is $\underline{\lambda}_o = [0.05, 0.05]$, $\bar{\lambda}_1 = [0.1, 0.05]$, $\underline{\lambda}_1 = [0, 0.05]$, $\bar{\lambda}_2 = [0.05, 0.1]$, $\underline{\lambda}_2 = [0.05, 0]$, and then solving two maximum/minimum conditioned problems for each time step, just like for the case of the single cracked beam. It is worth to mention that the considered five damage configurations do not correspond to those that would have been employed according to the vertex method. The monitored output parameter in this case is the transversal displacement at the midpoint of the beam, and the first three frequencies are considered with an associated damping equal to 0.05 for all the modes.

Figure 8. Interval time-domain response for the (a) beam subjected to a concentrated pulsating load: comparison between the exact results associated to a re-analysis (grey band) and (b) exact analyses associated to boundary intensities of damage and (c) response bounds obtained with the proposed approach.

In Figure 8a, it can be seen how the analyses considering the reference damage configuration (i.e. $\lambda_1 = \lambda_2 = 0.05$) and two limit conditions (i.e. $\lambda_1 = \lambda_2 = 0$ and $\lambda_1 = \lambda_2 = 0.1$), which incidentally

correspond to the analyses to be performed according to the approach proposed in [43], of the considered damage intervals do not lead to a correct evaluation of the bounds of the response (see for example the peaks at around 3.5 and 4 sec), since the bounds of the response can be associated to intermediate values of the damage severities. Both the applications reported in this section show that neither the vertex method nor the approach recently proposed in [43] can be effectively employed in the case of the forced vibration analysis of damaged beams. On the contrary, Figure 8b shows how the approach here proposed is able to effectively assess the bounds of the response for all the time history analysis, and in addition it is associated to a significantly lower computational burden.

5.2. Interval frequency-response curves

In the dynamics of structures a useful tool to summarize the behaviour of a structure subjected to frequency-dependent loads is the frequency-response curve. Basically, given a pulsating load with frequency ω applied to a structure, a frequency-response curve collects the magnification factor of the steady-state response with respect to the corresponding static response [48]. In an undamped deterministic analysis the frequency-response curve tends to diverge when ω assumes a value corresponding to each of the natural frequencies of the system (resonance phenomenon); even in presence of damping the peaks of the responses (not divergent) can be encountered in correspondence of the damped natural frequencies. When an uncertainty of the crack severity in a beam is considered, the natural frequencies can change significantly, as already shown in Figures 2-4; therefore, it is expected that an interval frequency-response band will show that the bounds of the response can be associated to values of the damage severities which do not coincide with the bounds of the considered interval.

To this purpose a further application is here proposed with reference to the beam reported in Figure 2a and subjected to a concentrated pulsating load at the midspan of the beam. The reference output

parameter is the transversal displacement at the abscissa corresponding to the midspan of the beam. The first five frequencies are accounted for and the re-analysis is associated to 31 analyses (considering a damage step $\Delta\lambda_1 = 0.01$). In Figures 9 and 10 the results are shown for two cases, that is the undamped system (Figure 9) and a damped system with damping equal to 0.05 for all the frequencies (Figure 10). For the undamped beam, in Figure 9a the steady-state response $u_{ss}(\xi_r)/u_{st}(\xi_r)$ at the desired abscissa normalized by the corresponding response of the beam when subjected to the static load versus the normalized frequency parameter of the pulsating load $\eta = \alpha_\omega^2/\alpha_{o,1}^2$ is reported. In addition, in order to show a different perspective of the results, Figure 9b plots the steady-state response $u_{ss}(\xi_r)$ at the desired abscissa, normalized by the corresponding response of the beam associated to the reference damage configuration $u_{ss,o}(\xi_r)$ versus η . Again, as already done in the previous section, the exact responses associated to three significant damage configurations are reported in the same plots, namely the reference configuration (i.e. $\lambda_1 = 0.15$), and those associated to the healthy beam (i.e. $\lambda_1 = 0$) and to the most severe configuration (i.e. $\lambda_1 = 0.3$) with solid, dashed, and dashdot lines, respectively. Such responses are not able to envelope correctly the grey area (see for example the second and the third resonance frequencies) and the classical vertex method does not seem suitable to assess the bounds of the response when an uncertainty in the damage intensities is introduced. In Figures 9c and 9d the bounds of the response obtained with the proposed approach are superimposed to the re-analysis envelope. Three main remarks can be made observing the latter results:

i) the proposed approximated explicit approach is able to bind the envelope obtained with the re-analysis for the whole considered range of the load frequency;

ii) the envelope obtained through re-analysis, being based on a discrete evaluation of the response for a finite number of values of the damage severity of the crack, is itself an approximated way to assess the actual envelope of the dynamic response; theoretically, the re-analysis is able to

regain the exact response variability only when an infinite number of values of the damage severities is considered;

iii) in this regard, the proposed approximated solution appears to be even more reliable than a re-analysis associated to a finite number of damage configurations (see for example the range $8 \leq \eta \leq 9$).

Figure 9. Frequency-response interval spectrum for the undamped beam reported in Figure 2a: comparison between the exact results associated to a re-analysis (grey band) and (a) exact analyses associated to boundary intensities of damage and (b) response bounds obtained with the proposed approach; (c,d) analogous results for the normalized response.

In Figure 10 the corresponding results for the damped system are reported. Similar considerations to those reported for the undamped system can be stated in this case too. It is worth highlighting that the representation provided in Figures 10c and 10d (and previously in Figures 9c and 9d) is able

to enhance and identify, for a given system, the range of η (i.e. the normalized frequency of the pulsating load) associated to a more pronounced dynamic response variability.

Figure 10. Frequency-response interval spectrum for the damped beam reported in Figure 2a: comparison between the exact results associated to a re-analysis (grey band) and (a) exact analyses associated to boundary intensities of damage and (b) response bounds obtained with the proposed approach; (c,d) analogous results for the normalized response.

Again, analogously to the results concerning the time history analyses, the dependency of the steady state response on the crack intensity is here investigated with reference to the undamped beam, whose results are summarized Figure 11. Three values of the pulsation were considered, namely $\eta = 4.5$ (Figure 11a), $\eta = 5.0$ (Figure 11b) and $\eta = 8.5$ (Figure 11c). In the first case a monotonic trend of the monitored response parameter is encountered as the damage intensity increases; in the second case a non monotonic trend is observed and, in addition, the response tends to diverge for a damage intensity $\lambda_1 \approx 0.1278$. A further remark to be highlighted is that, as the pulsation increases, and resonance effects occur in correspondence of higher frequencies, the

dependency between the steady state response and the crack intensity shows narrower spikes. The latter aspect implies that the search for the damage intensity corresponding to the upper bound of the response becomes more and more difficult if an explicit dependency on the damage intensity is not available.

Finally, accordingly to the previously reported applications, the frequency-response interval spectrum is inferred for the double cracked beam reported in Figure 8a. The results depicted in Figure 12 are relative to the damped system with damping equal to 0.05 for all the three considered frequencies. In Figures 12a and 12b, together with the grey area representing the envelope of the response obtained through re-analysis (considering 121 exact analyses associated to damage severity steps $\Delta\lambda_1 = \Delta\lambda_2 = 0.01$) the exact responses associated to three significant damage configurations are reported in the same plots, namely the reference configuration (i.e. $\lambda_1 = \lambda_2 = 0.05$), that associated to the healthy beam (i.e. $\lambda_1 = \lambda_2 = 0$) and to the most severe damage configuration (i.e. $\lambda_1 = \lambda_2 = 0.1$) with the continuous, the dashed, and the dashdot lines, respectively.

As already underlined in the previous applications, such limit configurations are not able to predict the bounds of the response in the considered damage intensity intervals (see for example $\eta \approx 9$). Figures 12c and 12d show that the proposed approach, even exhibiting a reduced precision with respect to the previous applications, at least in the central range of the frequency ratio ($7 \leq \eta \leq 12$), leads to conservative results, that never underestimate the actual response variability of the dynamic response.

Figure 11. Crack intensity vs steady state response for the beam reported in Figure 2a for specific frequency ratios: (a) $\eta=4.5$ (b) $\eta=5.0$ and (c) $\eta=8.5$.

Figure 12. Frequency-response interval spectrum for the beam reported in Figure 6a: comparison between the exact results associated to a re-analysis (grey band) and (a) exact analyses associated to boundary intensities of damage and (b) response bounds obtained with the proposed approach; (c,d) analogous results for the normalized response.

6 Inverse problem

The proposed explicit form of the modal parameter can be exploited to address the inverse problem aiming at the estimation of the damage magnitude in cracks whose positions are known (indeed the present procedure needs to be coupled to other strategies to detect the crack positions [13],[47],[52]-[54]). The possibility of deriving explicitly the damage intensities by considering experimental frequency measurements $\tilde{\alpha}_p^4$, being p the generic considered frequency, is explored. While the latter goal has been reached successfully for the crack identification by static tests [55]-[57], for the case of vibration measurements numerical procedures are commonly adopted [58]. Although the inverse problem for damage identification purposes was addressed considering explicit formulas of the

stationary second-order moments of the response [59], the only explicit expressions available in the literature providing explicitly the crack depth in terms of frequency measurements can be found in [52] and [60].

In order to formulate an alternative procedure able to deliver an explicit expression of the crack depth with respect to frequency measurements (for identification purposes) the expression of the p -th frequency parameter as a function of the crack depth parameter β_1 (as proposed in Eq. (23)), formulated for a beam with a single crack as follows

$$\alpha_p^4(\beta_1) \cong \alpha_{o,p}^4 + \frac{\beta_1 a_{p,1}}{1 + \beta_1 b_{p,1}}, \quad p = 1, \dots, n_m \quad (32)$$

can be employed. Once a single generic p -th frequency parameter appearing on the left-hand side is experimentally measured (named $\tilde{\alpha}_p^4$), Eq. (32) can be easily exploited to infer the parameter β_1 as follows:

$$\beta_1 = \frac{\tilde{\alpha}_p^4 - \alpha_{o,p}^4}{a_{p,1} - b_{p,1}(\tilde{\alpha}_p^4 - \alpha_{o,p}^4)} \quad (33)$$

Eq. (33) delivers the expression of the estimated crack depth $\lambda_1 = \lambda_{o,1} + \beta_1$ according to an explicit solution of the modal parameters conveniently calibrated. More precisely, Eq. (33) requires, based on the choice of the reference value of the damage $\lambda_{o,1}$ and of the deviation $\Delta\lambda_1$, the a priori evaluation of the p -th frequency parameter $\alpha_{o,p}^4$ and of the coefficients $a_{p,1}, b_{p,1}$, to be computed according to Eq. (28). However, it has to be pointed out that Eq.(33) does not require the preliminary measurement of the frequency of the healthy beam.

In case of presence of two cracks, the explicit expression provided by Eq. (23) can be written twice for the p -th and the q -th frequencies, which are considered given by experimental measures (named $\tilde{\alpha}_p^4, \tilde{\alpha}_q^4$), as follows:

$$\begin{cases} \tilde{\alpha}_p^4 = \alpha_{o,p}^4 + \frac{\beta_1 a_{p,1}}{1 + \beta_1 b_{p,1}} + \frac{\beta_2 a_{p,2}}{1 + \beta_2 b_{p,2}} \\ \tilde{\alpha}_q^4 = \alpha_{o,q}^4 + \frac{\beta_1 a_{q,1}}{1 + \beta_1 b_{q,1}} + \frac{\beta_2 a_{q,2}}{1 + \beta_2 b_{q,2}} \end{cases} \quad (34)$$

Eq. (34) after simple algebra leads to the following two-equation nonlinear system:

$$\begin{cases} (\tilde{\alpha}_p^4 - \alpha_{o,p}^4)(1 + \beta_1 b_{p,1} + \beta_2 b_{p,2}) = \beta_1 a_{p,1} + \beta_2 a_{p,2} + \beta_1 \beta_2 [b_{p,1} a_{p,2} + a_{p,1} b_{p,2} - b_{p,1} b_{p,2} (\tilde{\alpha}_p^4 - \alpha_{o,p}^4)] \\ (\tilde{\alpha}_q^4 - \alpha_{o,q}^4)(1 + \beta_1 b_{q,1} + \beta_2 b_{q,2}) = \beta_1 a_{q,1} + \beta_2 a_{q,2} + \beta_1 \beta_2 [a_{q,2} b_{q,1} + a_{q,1} b_{q,2} - b_{q,1} b_{q,2} (\tilde{\alpha}_q^4 - \alpha_{o,q}^4)] \end{cases} \quad (35)$$

Under the assumption of small cracks [61], and also by considering small intervals, the $\beta_1 \beta_2$ coupled terms can be neglected (as also proposed in [62]), and Eq. (35) can be linearised as follows:

$$\begin{cases} \tilde{\alpha}_p^4 - \alpha_{o,p}^4 = \beta_1 [a_{p,1} - b_{p,1} (\tilde{\alpha}_p^4 - \alpha_{o,p}^4)] + \beta_2 [a_{p,2} - b_{p,2} (\tilde{\alpha}_p^4 - \alpha_{o,p}^4)] \\ \tilde{\alpha}_q^4 - \alpha_{o,q}^4 = \beta_1 [a_{q,1} - b_{q,1} (\tilde{\alpha}_q^4 - \alpha_{o,q}^4)] + \beta_2 [a_{q,2} - b_{q,2} (\tilde{\alpha}_q^4 - \alpha_{o,q}^4)] \end{cases} \quad (36)$$

From the above linear system, once an explicit expression of the modal parameters is calibrated according to a reference damage configuration and to the relevant damage fluctuations, explicit expressions of the parameters β_1, β_2 can be straightforwardly inferred.

In general, for a multi-cracked beam, by linearizing the nonlinear system of equations, the following system of equations, based on the measurement of n frequencies $\tilde{\alpha}_p^4, p = 1, \dots, n$, can be inferred and easily solved:

$$\tilde{\alpha}_p^4 - \alpha_{o,p}^4 = \sum_{i=1}^n \beta_i [a_{p,i} - b_{p,i} (\tilde{\alpha}_p^4 - \alpha_{o,p}^4)] ; \quad p = 1, \dots, n \quad (37)$$

It is worth to mention that this approach always provides unique solutions since the damage intensity-frequency curves are always monotonically descending. Two main aspects would require additional detailed studies, that is the analysis of the sensitivity of the detection procedure to the

measurement errors, and the robustness of the procedure when the considered frequency does not activate a certain crack (i.e. the crack is located at a node for one of the considered fundamental modes). These aspects, which are common to many other identification procedures, fall outside the scope of the present work. In the following subsection the inverse procedure is tested for two simple cases.

6.1. Application of the inverse procedure to detect crack intensity in damaged beams

In order to test the reliability of the procedure described in the previous section, two cases are investigated, namely a single cracked beam and a double cracked one.

With regard to the single cracked beam, the damage is located at $\xi_1 = 0.4$, as shown in Figure 3a. The approximated solution is calibrated on the reference value of the damage $\lambda_{o,1} = 0.2$ and on the deviation $\Delta\lambda_1 = 0.2$. The actual value of the crack intensity is $\lambda_{1,r} = 0.05$, which has to be identified according to the procedure previously described, see Eq. (33). To this purpose a single frequency is sufficient to quantify the damage intensity.

No actual experimental campaign was made for this application. The values of the frequency adopted for testing the procedure are the outcome of exact computations, which are considered as given frequency data $\tilde{\alpha}_p^4$. It is worth to mention that no measurement error is introduced, since the focus of the study is to assess the error introduced by the proposed approximated explicit solution. In Table 5, the outcome of the identified damage intensity $\lambda_{1,i}$ employing each of the first four frequencies is reported along with the corresponding.

Table 5. Damage identification of a single cracked beam ($\xi_1 = 0.4$, $\lambda_{1,r} = 0.05$) for each of the first four frequencies.

p	$\tilde{\alpha}_p^4$	$\alpha_{o,p}^4$	$a_{p,1}$	$b_{p,1}$	$\lambda_{1,i}$	Error [%]
1	89.307	71.352	-95.938	1.318	0.04988	0.244
2	1510.266	1411.806	-494.731	1.628	0.04970	0.607
3	7646.638	7162.369	-2358.343	1.759	0.04916	1.687
4	23113.773	20390.137	-10958.631	2.5897	0.04879	2.424

As a further application the case of a double cracked beam is considered. In particular, the application is made with reference to the beam reported in Figure 4a. The crack positions are deterministic and located at the abscissae $\xi_1 = 0.4$ and $\xi_2 = 0.7$. The approximated solution is calibrated on the reference values of the damage $\lambda_{o,1} = 0.2$ and $\lambda_{o,2} = 0.1$ and on the deviation amplitudes $\Delta\lambda_1 = 0.2$ and $\Delta\lambda_2 = 0.1$. The actual damage intensities to be identified are $\lambda_{1,r} = 0.25$ and $\lambda_{2,r} = 0.15$. In this case the first two frequencies are employed and the linear system proposed in Eq. (36) is used to infer the damage intensities. The obtained results are summarized in Table 6.

Table 6. Damage identification of a double cracked beam ($\xi_1 = 0.4$, $\xi_2 = 0.7$ and $\lambda_{1,r} = 0.25$, $\lambda_{2,r} = 0.15$) considering the first two frequencies.

p	$\tilde{\alpha}_p^4$	$\alpha_{o,p}^4$	$a_{p,1}$	$b_{p,1}$	$a_{p,2}$	$b_{p,2}$	$\lambda_{1,i}$	Error [%]	$\lambda_{2,i}$	Error [%]
1	57.561	64.2795	-82.128	1.222	-64.605	0.865	0.2415	3.416	0.1621	8.094
2	953.179	1090.283	-779.569	1.914	-2266.052	2.952				

It is worth to note that the proposed procedure can be further improved by employing refining iterations calibrating, at each iteration, the approximated solution on the identified damage intensities identified at the previous iteration with progressively reduced deviations. In Table 7 the improvement on the identified damage intensities considering several iterations are presented

showing how after three iterations the error on the identified values rapidly decreases and becomes negligible.

Table 7. Damage identification of a double cracked beam ($\xi_1 = 0.4$, $\xi_2 = 0.7$ and $\lambda_{1,r} = 0.25$, $\lambda_{2,r} = 0.15$) considering the first two frequencies with an iterative procedure.

Iteration	$\lambda_{o,1}$	$\Delta\lambda_{o,1}$	$\lambda_{o,2}$	$\Delta\lambda_{o,2}$	$\lambda_{1,i}$	Error [%]	$\lambda_{2,i}$	Error [%]
1	0.2	0.2	0.1	0.1	0.2415	3.416	0.1621	8.094
2	0.2415	0.1	0.1621	0.05	0.2504	0.147	0.1495	0.342
3	0.2504	0.05	0.1495	0.025	0.2500	0.00019	0.1500	0.00049

7 Conclusions

Approximated explicit expressions of the main modal parameters (frequency parameters, generalized modal mass and load term) of continuous damaged beams are presented as a function of the damage severities. To this purpose, a model previously introduced for the deterministic dynamic analysis of multi-cracked beams is resorted to. It avoids the enforcing of continuity conditions at the cracked sections, according to a generalised function approach. The proposed approximated solutions are then employed to obtain explicit expressions of the response to the forced vibrations of cracked beams as well as to address inverse problems. With regard to the direct problem, the proposed strategy makes possible to easily infer the variability of the response associated to damage severities which are considered as uncertain parameters. The accuracy of the approximated approach for the evaluation of the modal parameters is assessed for single and multi cracked beams, with reference to transient time history analyses and the steady-state response. The proposed approach is computationally more convenient with respect to a brute scanning re-analysis approach (Monte Carlo simulations), and shows that for the forced vibrations of damaged structures the bounds of the response are not necessarily associated to the most and or least severe configurations, but might involve intermediate damage levels. With regard to the inverse problem,

the proposed explicit solution can be employed to detect the crack intensities of multi-cracked beam based on frequency measurements, by simply solving a linear system. Both the direct and inverse applications demonstrate the reliability and versatility of the proposed solution for addressing the dynamics of cracked beams.

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Appendix A. Orthogonality conditions

In this appendix the orthogonality condition of the modes evaluated according to the distribution theory is demonstrated following the strategy proposed in [63]. For a beam multiple cracks the generic p -th mode $\phi_p(\xi; \lambda)$ is ruled by the following equation:

$$\phi_p^{IV}(\xi; \lambda) - \alpha_p^4 \phi_p(\xi; \lambda) = \sum_{i=1}^n \lambda_i \phi_p''(\xi_i; \lambda) \delta''(\xi - \xi_i) \quad (\text{A1})$$

By multiplying Eq. (A1) for the r -th mode $\phi_r(\xi; \lambda)$ and integrating over the normalized beam span the following equation yields

$$\int_0^1 \phi_r(\xi; \lambda) \phi_p^{IV}(\xi; \lambda) d\xi - \alpha_p^4 \int_0^1 \phi_r(\xi; \lambda) \phi_p(\xi; \lambda) d\xi = \int_0^1 \phi_r(\xi; \lambda) \sum_{i=1}^n \lambda_i \phi_p''(\xi_i; \lambda) \delta''(\xi - \xi_i) d\xi \quad (\text{A2})$$

Integrating twice by parts, Eq. (A2) can be written as

$$\begin{aligned} & \phi_r(1; \lambda) \phi_p'''(1; \lambda) - \phi_r(0; \lambda) \phi_p'''(0; \lambda) - \phi_r'(1; \lambda) \phi_p''(1; \lambda) + \phi_r'(0; \lambda) \phi_p''(0; \lambda) + \\ & + \int_0^1 \phi_r''(\xi; \lambda) \phi_p''(\xi; \lambda) d\xi - \alpha_p^4 \int_0^1 \phi_r(\xi; \lambda) \phi_p(\xi; \lambda) d\xi = \int_0^1 \phi_r(\xi; \lambda) \sum_{i=1}^n \lambda_i \phi_p''(\xi_i; \lambda) \delta''(\xi - \xi_i) d\xi \end{aligned} \quad (\text{A3})$$

By collecting the terms in a simpler manner, Eq. (A3) becomes

$$\begin{aligned} & \int_0^1 \phi_r''(\xi; \lambda) \phi_p''(\xi; \lambda) d\xi - \alpha_p^4 \int_0^1 \phi_r(\xi; \lambda) \phi_p(\xi; \lambda) d\xi - \int_0^1 \phi_r(\xi; \lambda) \sum_{i=1}^n \lambda_i \phi_p''(\xi_i; \lambda) \delta''(\xi - \xi_i) d\xi = \\ & = -\phi_r(1; \lambda) \phi_p'''(1; \lambda) + \phi_r(0; \lambda) \phi_p'''(0; \lambda) + \phi_r'(1; \lambda) \phi_p''(1; \lambda) - \phi_r'(0; \lambda) \phi_p''(0; \lambda) \end{aligned} \quad (\text{A4})$$

The second member of Eq. (A4) represents the work done, by the end forces of the p -th mode for the corresponding displacements of the r -th mode. Since the nodal forces of the p -th mode are in equilibrium, the total work, computed for the set of nodal displacements associated with the r -th mod, is equal to zero. Based on this, it can be inferred that

$$\int_0^1 \phi_r''(\xi; \lambda) \phi_p''(\xi; \lambda) d\xi - \alpha_p^4 \int_0^1 \phi_r(\xi; \lambda) \phi_p(\xi; \lambda) d\xi - \int_0^1 \phi_r(\xi; \lambda) \sum_{i=1}^n \lambda_i \phi_p''(\xi_i; \lambda) \delta''(\xi - \xi_i) d\xi = 0 \quad (\text{A5})$$

By repeating the same procedure exchanging the considered modes, the following equation can be obtained

$$\int_0^1 \phi_p''(\xi; \lambda) \phi_r''(\xi; \lambda) d\xi - \alpha_r^4 \int_0^1 \phi_p(\xi; \lambda) \phi_r(\xi; \lambda) d\xi - \int_0^1 \phi_p(\xi; \lambda) \sum_{i=1}^n \lambda_i \phi_r''(\xi_i; \lambda) \delta''(\xi - \xi_i) d\xi = 0 \quad (\text{A6})$$

The first orthogonality condition can be obtained considering the difference between Eqs. (A5) and (A6)

$$\begin{aligned} & (\alpha_r^4 - \alpha_p^4) \int_0^1 \phi_p(\xi; \lambda) \phi_r(\xi; \lambda) d\xi + \int_0^1 \phi_p(\xi; \lambda) \sum_{i=1}^n \lambda_i \phi_r''(\xi_i; \lambda) \delta''(\xi - \xi_i) d\xi + \\ & - \int_0^1 \phi_r(\xi; \lambda) \sum_{i=1}^n \lambda_i \phi_p''(\xi_i; \lambda) \delta''(\xi - \xi_i) d\xi = 0 \end{aligned} \quad (\text{A7})$$

By integrating by parts twice the second and the third terms appearing in Eq. (A7) the following relations hold

$$\begin{aligned} \int_0^1 \phi_p(\xi; \lambda) \sum_{i=1}^n \lambda_i \phi_r''(\xi_i; \lambda) \delta''(\xi - \xi_i) d\xi &= \sum_{i=1}^n \lambda_i \phi_r''(\xi_i; \lambda) \int_0^1 \phi_p''(\xi; \lambda) \delta(\xi - \xi_i) d\xi = \sum_{i=1}^n \lambda_i \phi_r''(\xi_i; \lambda) \phi_p''(\xi_i; \lambda) \\ \int_0^1 \phi_r(\xi; \lambda) \sum_{i=1}^n \lambda_i \phi_p''(\xi_i; \lambda) \delta''(\xi - \xi_i) d\xi &= \sum_{i=1}^n \lambda_i \phi_p''(\xi_i; \lambda) \int_0^1 \phi_r''(\xi; \lambda) \delta(\xi - \xi_i) d\xi = \sum_{i=1}^n \lambda_i \phi_p''(\xi_i; \lambda) \phi_r''(\xi_i; \lambda) \end{aligned} \quad (\text{A8})$$

which leads Eq. (A7) to

$$(\alpha_r^4 - \alpha_p^4) \int_0^1 \phi_p(\xi; \lambda) \phi_r(\xi; \lambda) d\xi = 0 \quad (\text{A9})$$

that is

$$\int_0^1 \phi_p(\xi; \lambda) \phi_r(\xi; \lambda) d\xi = \begin{cases} 0 & p \neq r \\ M_p & p = r \end{cases} \quad (\text{A10})$$

The second orthogonality condition is obtained subtracting Eq. (A6), as multiplied by α_p^2 , from

Eq. (A5) as multiplied by α_r^2 , i.e.:

$$\begin{aligned} & (\alpha_r^2 - \alpha_p^2) \int_0^1 \phi_r''(\xi; \lambda) \phi_p''(\xi; \lambda) d\xi + \alpha_r^2 \alpha_p^2 (\alpha_r^2 - \alpha_p^2) \int_0^1 \phi_r(\xi; \lambda) \phi_p(\xi; \lambda) d\xi + \\ & - \alpha_r^2 \int_0^1 \phi_r(\xi; \lambda) \sum_{i=1}^n \lambda_i \phi_p''(\xi_i; \lambda) \delta''(\xi - \xi_i) d\xi + \alpha_p^2 \int_0^1 \phi_p(\xi; \lambda) \sum_{i=1}^n \lambda_i \phi_r''(\xi_i; \lambda) \delta''(\xi - \xi_i) d\xi = 0 \end{aligned} \quad (\text{A11})$$

Eq. (A11), in view of Eqs. (A8) and (A3), becomes

$$\begin{aligned}
 & (\alpha_r^2 - \alpha_p^2) \int_0^1 \phi_r(\xi; \lambda) \left[\phi_p^{IV}(\xi; \lambda) - \sum_{i=1}^n \lambda_i \phi_p''(\xi_i; \lambda) \delta''(\xi - \xi_i) \right] d\xi + \\
 & + \alpha_r^2 \alpha_p^2 (\alpha_r^2 - \alpha_p^2) \int_0^1 \phi_r(\xi; \lambda) \phi_p(\xi; \lambda) d\xi = 0
 \end{aligned} \tag{A12}$$

Finally, the second orthogonality condition, in view of Eq. (A10), can be formulated as:

$$\int_0^1 \phi_r(\xi; \lambda) \left[\phi_p^{IV}(\xi; \lambda) - \sum_{i=1}^n \lambda_i \phi_p''(\xi_i; \lambda) \delta''(\xi - \xi_i) \right] d\xi = \begin{cases} 0 & p \neq r \\ \alpha_p^4 M_p & p = r \end{cases} \tag{A13}$$